

Perspective of Employability Status and Career Development for Persons with Disabilities in Buea Municipality, Cameroon

Melem Linda Fangwi (PhD)

University of Buea, Cameroon

Abstract

Employment goes beyond hiring an individual into the world of work, but it ensures that he or she is given the opportunity for growth and development. Most people with disabilities are vulnerable to non-acquisition of skills for employment eligibility due to inequitable discrimination and rejection they often encounter during their education and quest for employment. This study investigated the educational status, employment accessibility, and career and employment progression avenues for persons with disabilities. It adopted the qualitative approach with the case study research design. A sample of 25 (12 females and 13 males) employees with disabilities and 20 (13 males and 7 females) employers of persons with disabilities in Buea municipality were purposively selected as participants in the study. Data was collected with the use of an interview guide and were analysed using descriptive statistics for biographic information and thematic analysis for qualitative data. The findings suggest that persons with disabilities who had due qualifications obtained employment commensurate with their qualifications. The study also realised that career progression avenues differ per job type and that most institutions and companies do not have a defined career progression path for persons with disabilities. It was therefore recommended that a multifaceted career development programme be instituted in various institutions and companies to facilitate the career growth for persons with disabilities.

Keywords: Career development; Disabilities; Employability Status; Perspective

Background

Career development, according to Kerka (2002, p. 4), is “a lifelong cyclical process that involves self-knowledge about personality, interests, skills, and abilities; understanding of the world of work and the requirements of specific occupations; and the aptitude to match one’s abilities and skills satisfactorily with an occupation and a work environment”. This process is full of challenges that range from personal, work context, collaborators, employers’ attitudes and more for persons without disabilities and much more for persons with disabilities, including issues related to occupational aspirations, self-efficacy expectations,

and career maturity; the list is inexhaustive. Persons with disabilities are people who, because of their impairment and the environment, have a reduced capability of activity to work, life and studies. This often results in different forms of impact based on the specific context, such as the environment (urban, rural), type of country (developed, less developed) and cultural/societal norms as related to people with disabilities (WHO, 2001).

Mitra, Posarac & Vick (2013) hold that, due to inaccessible school systems, many children with disabilities lack opportunities to receive training on vocational skills, which reduces their ability to accumulate capital and social assets as adults. Disparities in educational and employment rates among youths with disabilities are very high (Bogart & Dunn, 2019). According to the International Labour Organisation Statistic (ILOSTAT, 2022), in developing countries, the unemployment rate for persons with disabilities stands at 80-90%, while for those in the developed world, it stands at 50-70%. The global figure for employment is not specified; however, the specific country data by ILOSTAT shows that their employment rate in Cameroon stands at 30% (ILOSTAT, 2022).

According to Krause (2018), most employers still perceive disabilities from the medical model perspective: "Disability resides solely within the individual and focuses on 'fixing' or 'curing' the impairment" (p. 9). This view focuses on what a person with a disability is not capable of doing and cannot become; it thereby reinforces prejudice, discrimination, and social oppression towards people with disabilities (PWDA, 2021). Kasnitz (2020) postulates that the social model of disability sees the workplace as the reason for low productivity among employees with disabilities, and O'Shea et al. (2023) buttress that their experiences are limited by how the environment is constructed.

Rahmi and Rulanggi (2021) say the word *careerto* refers to one's involvement in a particular job family which includes multiple jobs and is a process that encompasses much of one's life span. It includes formal and informal experiences that give rise to talents, interests, values, knowledge of the world of work, and career behaviour and culminates with the transition into retirement (p. 3-5). Qiu, Jiang, Sun & Du (2023) and Hitchings & Retish (2000) identified the following factors as limitations to opportunities for career exploration for persons with disabilities: limited knowledge of the impact of disability on specific job performance, restricted early opportunities, dependence on family, experiences of academic failure, type and severity of disability, parental overprotectiveness, family low expectations, no comprehensive transition planning and more.

Employment is defined as the ability to create products or services to meet their own specific or society's requirements and receive compensation for his or her services or products. Zacher et al. (2019). It requires the signing of a contract of employment stipulating the terms of reference on the rights, responsibilities and work conditions. Employers could either be full-time and part-time, independent contractors, temporary employees, seasonal employees, fixed-term employees, casual workers, apprentices, trainees, interns, employed on commission, on probation, leased employees, contingent employees and more (Mitra, Posarac & Vick, 2013).

Statement of the Problem

Career development in this contemporary society involves an active participation of workers in planning career paths (Qiu, Jiang, Sun & Du, 2023). Despite decades of advances in special education practices, disability laws, and policies, postschool outcomes for most persons with disabilities remain dismal and below average in comparison to those without disabilities. They suffer from work-related discrimination such as accessing the job market, little chance for advancement, no opportunity for secondment, employers' stereotypes and attitudinal biases and more. It is against these that this study seeks to understand the career and employment development path for persons with disabilities in Cameroon.

Specifically, the study investigated

1. The educational status for job accessibility for persons with disabilities
2. Employment accessibility for eligible employees with disabilities
3. Career and employment progression avenue for employees with disabilities

Method

The study was qualitative in nature and made use of a workplace case study design to gather information on educational status, employment accessibility, and career and employment progression avenues for persons with disabilities. The population of the study was all employers and employees with disabilities in the Buea municipality of the Southwest region of Cameroon. 25 (12 females and 13 males) persons (employees) with disabilities and 20 (13 males and 7 females) employers of persons with disabilities in Buea municipality were purposively selected for this study. An interview guide was used to collect data from employees and employers of persons with disabilities and analyse it using descriptive statistics for biographic information and thematic analysis for qualitative data. The description of the sample is seen on Table 1.

Table 1: Description of respondents with disabilities

Disability Types	Nature of employer				GENDER	
	Public	Private	Mission	M	F	
Visual Impairment	09	01	00	06	04	
Physical disability	07	00	02	02	07	
Speech impairment	02	00	00	01	01	
Hearing impairment	00	04	00	03	01	
SUBTOTAL	18	05	02	12	13	

Table One presents a total of 25 employees with disabilities who participated in this study. Eighteen (18) of them worked in the public sector; that is, they are employees of the government of Cameroon, while four (04) are employed by the private sector and two (02) are employees of the mission. The table further demonstrates that among the twenty-five employees, thirteen (13) were females, while twelve (12) were males. The table also brings out the types of disabilities of the various employees as follows: visually impaired were ten (10), physically impaired seven (07), speech and language impaired two (02), and hearing impaired four (04). It could be concluded that in the Buea Municipality a segment of persons with disabilities have been employed; however, a stringent comparison could not be made because the total number of persons with disabilities living within this municipality is unknown.

Table 2: Description of employer respondents

Owner of Institution	Employing Institutions	Participating Employers			Disability Employed			
		No of Respondents	Gender		VI	PI	SI	HI
			M	F				
Public owned institutions	University of Buea	07	01	06	02	05	02	00
	Government Teacher Training College Buea	03	02	01	01	00	00	00
	Government Technical High School Molyko	02	01	01	01	00	00	00

	Government Bilingual High School Molyko-Buea	03	01	02	01	01	00	00
	Rehabilitation Institute for the Blind (RIB) Buea	01	01	00	05	00	00	00
Privately owned	Buea School for the Deaf	01	01	00	00	00	00	04
	Biaka University	01	01	00	01	00	00	00
	Law firm	01	01	00	00	01	00	00
Mission owned	Soppo field council of churches CBC	01	01	00	00	01	00	00
SUB-TOTAL	08	20	10	10	11	08	02	04
TOTAL			20	25				

Table 2 indicates a total of twenty (20) employers of persons with disabilities in various institutions, with five (05) public (state-owned) institutions (University of Buea, Government Teacher Training College Buea, Government Technical High School Molyko, Government Bilingual High School Molyko-Buea, and RIB Buea); two (03) privately owned institutions (Biaka University, Buea School for the Deaf, and an independent law firm); and one (01) mission institution (Soppo Field Council of Churches CBC). The table also discloses the number of respondents within each institution, with the University of Buea having the highest number of respondents, seven (07), followed by Government Teacher Training College Buea with three (03), Government Bilingual High School Molyko-Buea with three (03), Government Technical High School Molyko with three (02), and RIB Buea with one (01). The private institutions had had one (01) respondent each, and the mission also had one (01). The table further disclosed that the state-owned institutions have the highest number of employees with disabilities, with a total of eighteen (18) employees, while the private institution had a total of six (06) and the mission had one (01). Among the employees with disabilities, the University of Buea has employed two (02) visually impaired, five (05) physically impaired, and two (02) speech and language impaired. The Government Teacher Training College employed one (01) person with visual impairment, Government Technical High School Molyko employed one (01) person with visual impairment, and Government Bilingual High School Molyko-Buea employed one (01) person with visual impairment and one (01) person with physical impairment. The Rehabilitation Institute for the Blind (RIB) Buea employed five (05) persons with visual impairment. Among the private institutions in the Buea Municipality, the Biaka university institute has employed one (01) person with visual impairment on a part-time basis, while the Buea school for the deaf has recruited

four (04) persons with hearing impairment, and a private chamber has recruited one (01) person with physical impairment. It could therefore be concluded that the government of Cameroon is the highest employer of persons with disabilities within the Buea municipality.

Findings and discussion on the educational status for job accessibility for persons with disability

The educational status measures attainment in terms of certificates obtained and evaluates if the job is commensurate with the certification or if the employees are underemployed.

Table 3: Educational status of employees with disabilities and job type

Disability Types	Educational Attainment					Nature of job				
	Advance Level	Professional certification	Bachelor	Master	PhD	Teaching		AA	Law	Pastoring
						SEC	HEI			
Visual Impairment	00	02	02	01	03	07	03	00	00	00
Physical disability	00	03	05	01	02	03	02	02	01	01
Speech impairment	01	00	01	00	00	00	00	02	00	00
Hearing impairment	00	00	02	02	00	04	00	00	00	00
Total	01	05	10	04	05	14	05	04	01	01

Table 3 brings out information on educational attainment for each employee with disabilities sampled for this study. Among them, one (01) was a holder of the advance level certificate, five (05) had professional certificates in various professional domains, ten (10) out of the 25 respondents had bachelor’s degrees in various fields of study, while four (04) had master’s and five (05) had PhDs. The table also reveals the nature of jobs these persons with disabilities were employed to do. In the teaching domain, a total of seven (07) visually impaired, three (03) physically impaired and four (04) hearing impaired are teaching in

secondary schools within the Buea municipality. Still in the teaching domain, three (03) persons with visual impairments and two (02) others with physical impairments were teachers with some higher institutions of learning within the Buea municipality sampled for this study. The table also shows that a total of four (04) persons sampled for this study worked as administrative assistants, one (01) as a lawyer, and one (01) as a pastor. It is obvious that with due educational levels, persons with disabilities could be given a chance across various sectors of employment within the municipality. The employees have jobs that are commensurate with their obtained certificates.

These findings validate the following studies: Riddell and Song (2011), Woessmann (2016), and Bliksvær (2018) disclosed that educational attainment is a major determinant of employment rate among persons with disabilities. Albinowski, Magda and Rószczyńska (2023) hold that persons with disabilities from upper secondary schools have a 19% higher employment probability than those from primary schools. They believe that having completed tertiary education further increases the employment chances by over 20 per cent and that the difference in employment probability for persons with disabilities who have attained tertiary education and those with primary education stands at 39 per cent.

Bryan, Bryce Roberts and Sechel (2023) believed that many people with disabilities who are not employed are interested in being employed, and good employment brings a holistic flourishing. They stressed that working is key to poverty reduction, and persistent unemployment among certain groups is an underlying cause of inequality and reduced opportunities. The Joseph Rowntree Foundation (2022) postulates that among the working-age population, for persons with disabilities, the poverty rate is 38% more than twice that for persons without disabilities (17%).

Accessibility for employees with disabilities

Persons with disabilities perspective revealed *“Disability employment gap in Cameroon is very wide”*
“dignified and equitable access is a problem”

Employers' perspective *“Employment rate is very low with justifications”*

The findings showed that the majority of the respondents believed that the disability employment gap in Cameroon is very wide, with a low employment rate and thus no job satisfaction. Few employees with disabilities are satisfied with their current job situation. It is believed that people with disabilities have skills, experiences, and qualifications which can make them productive, reliable, and cost-effective, and they can occupy positions at the entry, middle management, and senior leadership levels, but dignified and equitable access is a problem for most of them, as described below:

Table 4: Challenges to dignified and equitable employment for persons with disabilities

Code	Themes
<p>“We have aspirations and interest as anyone else but lack of dignified and equitable access to jobs, tailored professional development, inaccessible workplaces through the manifestation of unconscious and conscious biases, are barriers that holds us back, not our aspirations...”.</p> <p>“Most employers incorrectly assume that employees with disabilities do not want challenging assignment which impact their decision about us at all stages of employment...”</p> <p>I was not considered for a job because they said since I am visually impaired, I need another person to assist me in doing my job and the institution does not have money for such ... I left and never imagined I could be employed in such an institution”</p>	Lack of dignified and equitable access
	Lack of tailored professional development
	Manifestation of unconscious biases
	Employers’ negative perception of persons with disabilities
	Persons with disabilities are demotivated

“Lack of dignified and equitable access”: This ensures that people with impairments should have the same opportunity as those without and should access all parts of the workplace network with the same comfort levels. Dignified and equitable access is not just a legal or moral obligation but a fundamental aspect of building a truly inclusive workplace. It is characterised by the provision of reasonable adjustments such as a height-adjustable desk for persons using wheelchairs, screen reading software for those with visual impairments, modifications in working hours to allow for effectiveness for those with cognitive and attention issues, provision of special equipment, modifications to work vehicles, information and communication devices, specialist services for employees with specific learning disorders and mental

health conditions, disability awareness training, mental health first aid training and more. All these are missing in most institutions and companies in Cameroon.

“Lack of Tailored Professional Development” (TPD): This is an ongoing activity in which a professional identifies, undertakes, and evaluates appropriate learning opportunities to maintain and develop the highest standards of practice within their professional space. It plays a pivotal role in that training programmes are aligned with the specific requirements and goals of a given profession. This is beneficial to various institutions, as it gives skills beneficial to specific units in an institution/organisation. TPD can be effectively done when a thorough needs analysis is conducted. The needs assessments will identify gaps in knowledge, skills, and competencies and prioritise training initiatives accordingly. Most persons with disabilities have knowledge, skills and competences which do not match the requirements of most institutions and organisations for adequate employment. The training institutions therefore need to work hand in gloves with employers to ensure that the knowledge, skills and competences gaps are identified, and effective training is conducted to close these gaps and thereby provide employment opportunities for others. TPD will help employees with disabilities to access work opportunities by actively facilitating the acquisition of relevant knowledge. There is not liaison between most employers and the training institution as such people are trained with skills that are over-represented in most institutions and organisations.

Manifestation of unconscious, implicit or hidden biases: These are human prejudices about people or groups of people and involve quick assessments of people and situations based on one’s own background, culture and personal experiences. Most often unconscious biases are triggered by people’s first impressions and intuitions about others. It is outside one’s control, though steps could be taken to mitigate its effects. Often, the environment and experiences reinforce it, leading to the formation of a pattern of behaviour. Employers who participated in the study also acknowledged the fact that there are hindrances to equitable and dignified access to employment for persons with disabilities, such as negative attitudes by employers, discrimination, and lack of trust in the potential and skills possessed by these persons with disabilities, and they further declared that *“the employment of people with disabilities is a matter of social inclusion and not of charity. All employees are given duties that are of importance for the institution, which means that the employees with disabilities aren’t there only to fulfil the quota requirements but also to be included in the workplace together with the rest of the staff. If they don’t meet the institution’s goals, they can be fired like any other employee.”*

To buttress this they also declared that *“Small steps lead to big changes its time employers focus on removing barriers in the recruitment process for people with disability and improve their unconscious negative attitudes and beliefs in order to acknowledge that employees with disability have unique skills and like any other they should be given equal opportunities to participate in professional development and leadership, ensure workplace adjustments, leverage systems and programs to enable the development of employees with disabilities this will help the institution/organisations gain a competitive edge in the national and international platform.”*

Employers acknowledged that the employment opportunities for persons with disabilities have not been the best and therefore call on other employers to give them opportunities commensurate to their qualifications. Understanding subconscious and unconscious bias is key to mitigating its impact. It facilitates the questioning of assumptions and eases the management of biases in personal and work-related decision-making. By acknowledging and addressing these biases, employers would make more informed and fair-minded choices with minimal discrimination (Bryan, Bryce Roberts and Sechel, 2023).

Career and employment progression avenue for employees with disabilities

Interview analysis of employees and employers: Career progression is about growth and development in one’s professional life, it is advancement in one’s professional journey including promotions, increased responsibility, skill development, networking opportunities and career change. Every employee desire growth and development but for the most part few attain the heights they all envisage.

Employers' perspective on Career and employment progression avenue

The employers who participated disclosed that career progression is mandatory in terms of law but for internal growth such as secondment it is at the discretion of the worker’s immediate boss. *“Career progression path for all workers is mandatory in public higher institutions of learning Therefore, promotion from one grade to the next for those employed as teachers in higher education, secondment, teamwork, and mentorship programs through supervision of students were identified as career development avenues for those in HEIs” but, in terms of internal growth opportunities, it is at the discretion of the authority that be. sometimes I assign them on secondment, teamwork, they also have students they mentor through supervision officially assigned to them by the department. However, for support staffs in HEIs their career progression path is not fully defined”*

The employers disclosed the following as career progression opportunities: promotion from one grade to the next for those employed as teachers in higher education, secondment, teamwork, and mentorship programs through supervision of students. Another view was raised by those in secondary and basic education.

“Being in secondary schools we do not really have any well laid down path for career progression as a teacher of history you will remain a teacher of history no path to follow however the only thing I do is to encourage them to continue schooling and build their skills via formal schooling opportunities, workshops, seminars, we also make recommendations for them to partner with other institutions, build networks, and more this brings a lot of fulfilment to them and when they come back they come with new vigor to keep teaching”. Career progression opportunities in secondary education are limited just to secondment, educational and skill development through formal schooling opportunities, workshops, seminars, and the building networks with other professionals for greater exposure.

Employment is not just about being hired into the world of work but ensuring that employees are given growth and development opportunities. Employees with disabilities should have equal opportunities to advance in their employment and build networks like all other. This could be via the provision of accommodations, such as assistive technologies, as well as appropriate training for skills development to enable them grow in their career (de Jonge, Scherer & Rodger, 2007).

Most employers hold that employees with disabilities are competent enough for career progression and encourages them to go back to school for upskilling and attend workshops and seminars and establish networks and partner with other institutions. They disclosed that career progression in Cameroon is well defined for some profession but for others it is not, such as, for the military and teachers in higher education but for teachers in primary and secondary schools it is not defined. Employees with disabilities in higher education follow the same channel of progression laid down by the laws governing higher educational institutions in Cameroon. However, in higher education the growth structure is well laid down for academic staff but for the support staff there is no stipulated or laid down path, once a secretary for ever a secretary or a change of job. Employees revealed their perspective on career and employment progression avenue as follows:

“Career progression is not an issue for us lecturers in higher education in Cameroon this is because the career progression path is well stipulated, but this is not the case for support staff.”

“As support staff we have no clear career progression path except if you further your education then you can move from one service to the other with an increase in salary scale” “We rarely have workshops, seminars, mentorship nor job shadowing programs”.

“Being in secondary schools we do not really have any well laid down path for career progression, but we do have workshops, seminars, and more”

It is obvious that the career progression path for administrative assistance, secretaries and other support staff in the university and other institution is not clearly defined by policy. Thus, institutions rarely organised seminars for them, they most often do not have opportunities for secondment nor job shadowing, no mentorship programs for them across the country.

What in your opinion is the reason why companies/institutions do not have clear career progression avenue for persons with disabilities?

From the employer's perspective, the following were identified as challenges to career progression for employees with disabilities: Most of the respondents disclosed that *"Most companies and institutions upon creation never thought of recruiting persons with disabilities it is only when they are recruited that they struggle to make some modifications to accommodate them however as pointed by the participants in the study ensuring workplace adjustments becomes challenging when doing it without any policy stipulations, administrators accommodate workers with disabilities as though they are doing personal favour to them..., systems are not flexible, building inclusion into the everyday activities in most institutions, removing barriers building informal networking and development opportunities as well as team building opportunities are impossibilities..."* Persons with disabilities meet with a lot of hindrances on their career progression path such as unconscious biases, *Inadequate workplace adjustment*, no adapted training facilities and programs, inadequate workplace adaptation, lack of support network, lack of inclusive organisational or institutional culture, inadequate preparation and poor planning, no institutional/companies' policy on career progression and more.

The above findings are in congruence with Mitra, Posarac and Vick (2013) report on challenges to career progression for persons with disabilities, which stated that unconscious biases are automatic judgement and stereotypes that influence our perceptions, decisions and actions without one's awareness. In a work environment, unconscious biases have several implications: talented people are left out of the workforce, there is unequal opportunity for development, diverse voices are not heard in meetings, and there are impaired decisions, compromised creativity and productivity of teams and more. Persons with disabilities face marginalisation and social, economic, and civic disparities because of unconscious biases from employers and other workers, and disability-based marginalisation results in exclusion, isolation, and abuse. Metts (2000). Hitchings and Retish (2000) pointed out that many employees with disabilities lack understanding of their disability and its impact on their career choices.

Drobnic (2023) holds that career development and progression for most persons with disabilities is an uphill task due to a deficit in the twenty-first century employability skills which is the strength of the times. These skills include soft skills such as communication skills (verbal, non-verbal & listening skills),

adaptability and flexibility, emotional intelligence, time management and organisational skills, networking/relationship building, work ethics/professionalism, and problem-solving skills (analytical and logical thinking). The technical skills such as digital literacy, coding and programming, blockchain technology, artificial intelligence and machine learning, digital marketing, cloud computing, data literacy and analytics. Thus, building and equipping persons with disabilities with the twenty-first-century skills will enhance their probability of getting a job and progressing in that job.

The justification for the low employment status of persons with disabilities could be due to hidden productivity differences, not necessarily related to their impairment status as stipulated by the medical model of disability (Jones and Wass, 2013). In this model, a person's impairment directly reduces their ability to function in society. Whereas the social model stipulates that reduced functioning arises because social institutions and practices are not adapted to impairments. Thus, society disables people with impairments by their social structures because impairments do not equal disability (Chandola & Rouxel, 2021, and Jones & McVicar, 2020).

It was therefore recommended that for better career progression for persons with disabilities, workplace accommodations such as flexible schedules, assistive technology, career counselling and mentorship opportunities, awareness training and campaigns, accessible environments, attitude change, and the establishment of internal career progression avenues such as secondment, education for upskilling, networking, mentorship and more be made mandatory for every institution and company.

Also, the implementation of teaching strategies that fosters the acquisition of the twenty-first century employability skills, such as the use of the universal design for learning, differentiated instruction, technology and assistive technology integration, collaborative learning, and the integration of cultural strategies in teaching, such as storytelling, proverbs, and oral traditions, be reinforced in various teaching institutions.

Moreover, creating formal groups such as disability employee networks (DENs) and workplace mentoring programmes will benefit employees with disabilities because it serves as a platform for sharing information and initiatives, building supportive relationships, and improving organisational systems.

Conclusion

This study aimed at revealing the perspective of employability status and career development for persons with disabilities in Buea municipality and has presented the educational status for job accessibility, eligibility for employment, and career and employment progression avenues for employees with disabilities. It is believed that people with disabilities have skills, experiences, and qualifications which

enable them to be productive, reliable, cost-effective, and capable of occupying positions at the entry, middle management, and senior leadership levels, but dignified and equitable access is a problem for most of them due to numerous challenges. It was therefore recommended that a multifaceted career development programme be instituted in various institutions and companies to facilitate career growth and development.

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